

PHYTOCHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITIES OF FRUIT EXTRACTS OF *Xylopi aethiopica* ON SOME CLINICAL ORGANISMS

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Abstract: The present study was designed to evaluate the phytochemical and antibacterial properties of fruit extracts of *Xylopi aethiopica* on selected clinical isolates. The clinical isolates obtained from a high grade medical laboratory center which includes *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were confirmed using biochemical tests and then standardized with 0.5 McFarland. Standard techniques were used in crude extraction followed by phytochemical screening. The antibacterial activities of the different extracts were investigated using agar diffusion and broth microdilution methods. Findings revealed that *Xylopi aethiopica* fruit extracts was found to contain flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins, alkaloids and cardiac glycosides. Antibacterial activities showed that ethanol and aqueous fruit extracts possessed inhibitory effects on *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* that ranged between 9mm to 18mm, 7mm to 15.5mm and 6mm to 12 mm respectively and 9mm to 15mm, 7mm to 12mm and 6mm to 8.5mm respectively. Among all strains tested, *S. aureus* and *E. coli* showed the best sensitivity with a MIC of 50 mg/mL. The findings indicate that *Xylopi aethiopica* have potential to mitigate bacterial infections and reduce reliance on synthetic antibiotics.

Keywords: *Xylopi aethiopica*, Extracts, Phytochemical, Antibacterial, Isolates.

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditional medicine is a possible substitute for the healthcare delivery system for a large portion of the world's population. The search for agents to cure infectious diseases began long before people were aware of the existence of microbes. These early attempts used natural substances, usually whole plants or their extracts and many of these herbal remedies proved successful.

Xylopi aethiopica, commonly known as "Ethiopian pepper" or "Guinea pepper," is an aromatic tree that belongs to the family of Annonaceae. It is widely used in ethnomedicine for managing various ailments including skin infections, candidiasis, dyspepsia, cough and fever (Ekpiken *et al.*, 2023). Some studies have also demonstrated the efficacy of *X. aethiopica* oil as anticancer, antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anticholinesterase, antimalarial, antitrypanosomal, antidepressant and insecticidal (Ndoye *et al.*, 2024).

Plants are rich in a variety of secondary metabolites. These phytochemical compounds which are present in any part of a plant have been reported to have antimicrobial properties in vitro. Phytochemical compounds confer high medicinal potency on plants enabling them to be used as a source of raw materials for the production of many drugs (Ekpiken *et al.*, 2023).

Treatment of infectious diseases has been threatened by the emergence and spread of antibiotic resistant organisms which has significant public health concerns (Manandhar *et al.*, 2019). There is therefore, urgent need to find new antimicrobial agents as alternative therapy. Hence, this study was undertaken to investigate the phytochemical and antimicrobial properties of the different fruit extracts of *Xylopiya aethiopic*.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

COLLECTION OF PLANT MATERIALS

The plant material *Xylopiya aethiopic* fruit was purchased from local vegetable market in Aba North Local Government Area of Abia State. The plant material was transported to the department of Biology/Microbiology for taxonomic identification.

PREPARATION OF SAMPLE AND EXTRACTION PROCEDURE

The plant materials; fruits of *Xylopiya aethiopic* was air dried at room temperature under a shade and ground into uniform powder using electric blender. Maceration method was adopted for aqueous and ethanol extraction, where 200g of the plant fruit powder was weighed into different clean grease free glass container and 500ml of each of the solvents was added into different containers containing plant powder, shake vigorously, and allowed to stand for 24 hours. The extracts were filtered separately using muslin cloth and concentrated using a water bath at a temperature of 60°C. Different concentrations of the extracts were prepared, such as 25 mg/ml, 50 mg/ml, 75 mg/ml and 100mg/ml respectively.

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF FRUIT EXTRACT OF *Xylopiya aethiopic*

Extracts were qualitatively screened for phytochemicals of medicinal importance following standard protocols described by Aguru *et al.* (2016).

TEST MICROORGANISMS

The organisms used for the test were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The stock cultures were obtained from a high grade medical laboratory in Aba, Abia State, Nigeria

ANTIBACTERIAL SCREENING

The agar well diffusion method was used to screen the antibacterial activity of various extract of seeds of *Xylopiya aethiopic*. Nutrient agar plates were prepared for bacteria isolates and each plate was inoculated with pathogens. 8mm well was cut on the agar plate surface using a sterile borer. Four different concentrations (25mg/ml, 50mg/ml, 75mg/ml, and 100mg/ml) of the extract was added to the well. The plates were incubated for 24 hours at 37°C for bacteria. After incubation the plates were observed for zone of inhibition around the well. The zones were measured with a transparent ruler and the result recorded.

DETERMINATION OF MINIMUM INHIBITORY CONCENTRATION (MIC)

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *Xylopiya aethiopic* seed extracts were determined using microbroth dilution technique described by Emeh *et al.* (2020). The extracts were diluted ranging from 100mg/ml to 5mg/ml and checked for MIC against bacterial isolates after 24 hours.

3. RESULTS

Table (1) summarizes the phytochemical screening of ethanol and aqueous crude extracts of *X. aethiopic* fruits. The fruit extracts show the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, saponins and terpenoids. Table 2 reveals the extracts showed maximum inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus* (18mm) followed by *Escherichia coli* (15mm) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (12mm). Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the extracts of *Xylopiya aethiopic* seed on test isolates is shown in table 3 revealed 50mg/ml for *Escherichia coli*, 50 mg/ml for *Staphylococcus aureus* and 100mg/ml for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Table 1: Phytochemical screening of ethanol and aqueous crude extracts of *X. aethiopica* fruits.

Bioactive components of the plant <i>X. aethiopica</i> fruits	Ethanol	Aqueous
Alkaloids	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+
Saponins	+	+
Tannins	-	-
Cardiac glycosides	+	+
Terpenoids	+	+
Anthraquinones	-	-

Table 2: Antimicrobial activities of *Xylopi* *aethiopica* fruit aqueous and ethanolic extracts on clinical isolates

TEST ISOLATES	Zone of Inhibition(mm)/Concentration (mg/ml)								
	Ethanol				Aqueous				Control (µg/ml)
	100	75	50	25	100	75	50	25	Streptomycin
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	15.5	13	10	08	12	10	07	-	25
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	18	16	13	11	15	13	12	09	21.5
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	12	09	08	05	8.5	06	-	-	27

Table 3: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

Isolates	Conc. (mg/ml)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	50
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	50
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	100

4. DISCUSSION

The results of phytochemical and antimicrobial screening of *Xylopi* *aethiopica* fruit extracts showed that the plant contain some bioactive substances which is evident in the various zones of inhibitions observed against bacteria organisms tested. These bioactive substances are alkaloids, terpenoids, saponins, flavonoids and cardiac glycosides. This result confirms reports of Ngwoke *et al.* (2015) and Aguoru *et al.* (2016) who reported presence of these phytochemical substances as observed in this study.

The findings of the study demonstrates remarkable antibacterial activities of ethanol extracts from *Xylopi* *aethiopica* fruits against various test bacterial isolates and its effectiveness varies depending on the bacterial strain. The results also revealed that the extracts exhibited increased antibacterial activity as the concentration increased. Some studies have confirmed that extracts of various parts of the plant through *in vitro* studies have anti-microbial activity. For instance, Musbau *et al.* (2024) reported that both ethanol and chloroform extracts displayed significant antibacterial activity *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Shigella boydii* and *Klebsiella oxytoca* which was comparable to reference drug, amikacin. Ezenobi *et al.* (2023) research work also confirmed the antimicrobial activity of *Xylopi* *aethiopica* fresh fruit extract against *Candida albicans*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Reports on the ethnopharmacological uses of various parts of *X. aethiopica* supports these findings.

Although *Xylopi* *aethiopica* has shown to be of potential pharmacological benefits, research and published data on pre-clinical and clinical studies conducted on its bioactive constituents are largely lacking. There is therefore the need for further research to be conducted on various extracts of *Xylopi* *aethiopica* in diseased conditions both in *in vitro* and animal studies to ascertain its potency, safety and efficacy in humans.

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